

**DIAGNOSIS OF THE COMPONENTS OF SELF-
ORGANIZATION OF LEARNING AND COGNITIVE ACTIVITY
OF MEDICAL COLLEGES STUDENTS**

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**ДІАГНОСТИКА КОМПОНЕНТІВ САМООРГАНІЗАЦІЇ
НАВЧАЛЬНО-ПІЗНАВАЛЬНОЇ ДІЯЛЬНОСТІ СТУДЕНТІВ
МЕДИЧНИХ КОЛЕДЖІВ**

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The article discloses the research base criteria for self-organization of learning and cognitive activity of students of medical colleges. The author argues that a high level of quality education is impossible without realization of self-organization of learning and cognitive activity by students. The motivational target, organizational planning, operational and executive, reflective and regulatory structural components of self-organization of learning and cognitive activity of students of medical colleges are determined, the content of which is considered when selecting the base of criteria of the study: motivational and personal, cognitive, action-effective, reflective criteria. It is set that on motivational and personal criterion for diagnostic and modeling stage of the technology of providing self-organization of learning and cognitive activity students of medical colleges have insufficient focus on self-organization.

Key words: self-organization, criterion, student, learning and cognitive activity, motivation.

Problem statement. One of the priority tasks facing higher medical educational establishments is to improve the educational process that will bring the quality of a health professional with the requirements of modern science and practice. The quality of education is defined as a system of socially constructed indicators of level of knowledge, skills, value attitude to the world, which should have a future professional [9]. Achieving high quality education is impossible without realization of self-organization of learning and cognitive activity by students because providing the appropriate level of knowledge, skills and professional qualities of a student, involving him in independent acquisition of knowledge in the future professional activity depends primarily on the student's attitude to learning, skills of planning and analyzing his activity, rational use of his time. Therefore, self-organization of learning and cognitive activity of students is one of the factors of efficiency of educational process that promotes revitalization, optimization and improvement of the learning process, and as a result provides quality professional training.

Analysis of recent researches. Analysis of psychological and educational literature allows to distinguish scientific works, which highlight the issue of problems of self-organization in the educational process of higher educational establishments: the organization of independent work of students (S. Amirova, A. Belyaeva, N. Koryakovtseva, G. Mykhailenko, P. Pidkasystyy, I. Shymko); forming a rational educational activity (N. Rybakova); the interrelation of self-organization and motivation of learning activity (H. Kogan); the interrelation of self-organization and self-control (J. Ustinova); creating a culture of self-organization (G. Hmyzina); interrelation of self-organization components and academic progress (O. Ishkov); forming self-organization techniques (V. Lvovych).

It should also be noted that constant attention is paid to the improvement of the educational process in higher medical education. Certain aspects of diagnosis of health professionals' training at the college are studied in the recent researches. Thus, studying the nurses' training, O. Kovalenko [4] developed a quotient-criteria model for evaluating levels of independence, which allowed determining the level of development and the degree of expression of medical students' independence. Criteria for formation of the cognitive activity of students while studying natural sciences were determined by T. Temerivska [8].

Since increasing students' readiness for realization of self-organization is important in education at medical college, the base of criteria of self-

organization of learning and cognitive activity requires clarification and improvement.

The aim of the article is to justify the criteria basis for self-organization of learning and cognitive activity of students of medical colleges and to present the results of diagnostics of its motivational target component.

Problem statement. In the context of our study we consider the self-organization of learning and cognitive activity of students as a conscious activity of students associated with the skills to organize themselves in the learning process, which is manifested in the commitment, active, conscious motivation, planning their activities, independence, rapidity of making decision and responsibility for them, critical assessment of the results of their actions, a sense of duty. In the process of self-organization skills and personal qualities that ensure the effectiveness of learning and cognitive activity of students are formed. Student's learning and cognitive activity is based on positive motivation, personal qualities of the student as a subject of learning, and is aimed at the formation of the student as a person who has the ability to self-organize own activities.

In the structure of self-organization of learning and cognitive activity of students we determined the following components: motivational target, organizational planning, operational and executive, reflective-regulatory. Such self-structuring covers all activities of students in the learning process.

The motivational target component of self-organization of learning and cognitive activity of students is characterized by the formulation of goals of their own self-organization, determination of their own tasks, students' focus on realizing the content of this activity and the expected result.

The organizational and planning component of self-organization of learning and cognitive activity is characterized by the planning process of learning: the content of self-organization is defined; planning and design of certain processes of self-organization of learning and cognitive activity are being performed.

The operational and executive component of self-organization of learning and cognitive activity is to implement learning and cognitive activity organized accordingly.

The reflective-regulatory component is systematical feedback on the progress and results of learning and cognitive activity, provides student's self-regulation the process of self-organization.

To determine the effectiveness of the technology of providing self-organization of learning and cognitive activity of students according to the purpose and tasks of the study we substantiated a set of criteria and related indicators of self-organization of future medical professionals.

The term “criterion” (from the Greek criterion – means for judging) we understand as “generalized indicator the development of a system, success of activity, the basis for classification ... a key feature of the observed object on which assessment is carried out” [6, p. 42], and the essence of the definition of “indicator” as measured characteristics of “an aspect of “key” feature (criteria) of the object, which gives a quantitative or qualitative information about its specific properties” [6, p. 49].

J. Ustinova and S. Kotova to determine the formation levels of skills of self-organization and self-control of learning activity [10] and competences of self-organization of students’ learning-professional activity [5] define the following criteria: knowledge of the theory of self-organization and self-control, their availability and quality; the level of practical knowledge skills and competencies that ensure the success of the process of self-organization and self-control of learning and learning-professional activity; awareness, appropriateness and systematic implementation of self-organization and self-control learning and learning-professional activity.

Investigating the formation of professional skills of self-organization, L. Faleeva developed the following criteria for assessing the levels of professional skills of self-organization: cognitive, operational, diagnostic [11].

A. Kirillova includes the following factors to the criteria of forming students’ self-organization: the level of development of the cognitive component; the level of formation of the functional component; the level of formation of the personal component of self-organization [3].

When choosing the research base of criteria we take into account the content of the structural components of self-organization of learning and cognitive activity of students of medical colleges.

In view of the above-mentioned, the following criteria and indicators of self-organization of learning and cognitive activity of students of medical colleges were determined: a) *motivational and personal* (attitude to training and to independent work in particular, professional and educational interest, awareness of the importance self-organization to improve the quality of training, moral and volitional qualities); b) *cognitive* (knowledge of self-organization of learning and cognitive activity, cognitive activity, cognitive independence); c)

action-effective (formation of skills of self-organization of learning and cognitive activity of students, the level of educational achievement); d) *reflective* (reflective skills formation, the adequacy of self-assessment, the level of self-assessment).

In order to ascertain the level of self-organization students according to motivational and personal criterion for diagnostic and modeling stage of the technology of providing self-organization of learning and cognitive activity among medical colleges students there was used a complex of scientific and pedagogical research methods (observation, interviews, questionnaires, tests) and diagnostic techniques, including “Motivation of learning in higher educational establishments” (T. Ilyina [1]), “Study of motives of students’ learning activity” (A. Rean, V. Yakunin [1]), “diagnostics of features of self-organization” (O. Ishkov [2]).

The study was conducted in academic groups of Medical College of Kharkiv National Medical University and Municipal Health Care Establishment “Kharkiv Medical College № 2” during 2012–2015. 321 students took part in the study.

In the process of diagnosis the students’ level of desire to acquire knowledge and their curiosity was determined. 49.8% of students study subjects required for their future profession. 54.2% of respondents think that the full acquisition of the profession requires equal thoroughness of learning all disciplines. 75.6% of students consider own willpower for training sufficient. 49.4% responded positively to the statement: “I’m doing the best when I am occasionally stimulated”.

The scale “acquirement of the profession” contained a statement to clarify the desire of students to acquire professional knowledge and form good professional quality. Among the first-year students 62% tell friends about their future profession with pleasure. 55.4% of students associate their admiration with future work. 62.6% of respondents consider the choice of the educational establishments as a final one. 60.8% responded that they were interested in the profession of health professional before entering the educational establishment. 66.8% of students consider this profession the most important and the most promising.

These studies allowed to define priority motives of learning and cognitive activity of students: to become highly qualified specialist – 88%; to obtain deep and strong knowledge – 73%; ensure the success of future professional activity – 51.6%.

To identify difficulties and contributing factors of self-organization of medical colleges there was conducted a survey of students' individual characteristics "Students' self-esteem of individual factors of own self-organization of learning and cognitive activity".

Thus, the survey indicated possible to ascertain the level of students' willpower in learning. 58% of students said that can work despite the immediate emotional impulses, 74% – direct their efforts to create opportunities to achieve this aim, 58% – successfully overcome situational desires that distract from particular purpose.

In the proposed statement to determine the level of planning of their own activities, students responded positively: "I make a work plan for the week" (10%), "at the end of the day I analyze where and for what reasons I wasted time" (37%), "I plan own work the next day" (68%), "I use a system for fixing assignments, tasks" (16%).

The research allowed finding out that students have positive motivation to study and future career, a sufficient level of willpower, but are not able to plan their activities, to use the time rationally.

Conclusion. The criteria basis of the study is the following criteria: motivational and personal, cognitive, action-effective, reflective – and related indicators that give an opportunity to get objective results about the studied phenomenon.

According to the study it was found that for motivational and personal criterion of self-organization of learning and cognitive activity despite positive professional motivation students have a lack of focus on self-organization.

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Гук І. П. Діагностика компонентів самоорганізації навчально-пізнавальної діяльності студентів медичних коледжів. У статті обґрунтовано критеріальну базу дослідження самоорганізації навчально-пізнавальної діяльності студентів медичних коледжів. Автор стверджує, що досягти високого рівня якості навчання неможливо без здійснення студентами самоорганізації навчально-пізнавальної діяльності. Виокремлено мотиваційно-цільовий, організаційно-планувальний, операційно-виконавчий, рефлексивно-регулятивний структурні компоненти самоорганізації навчально-пізнавальної діяльності студентів медичних коледжів, зміст яких враховано при виборі критеріальної бази дослідження: мотиваційно-особистісний, когнітивний, діяльнісно-результативний, рефлексивний критерії. З'ясовано, що за мотиваційно-особистісним критерієм на діагностико-моделювальному етапі технології забезпечення самоорганізації навчально-пізнавальної діяльності

студенти медичних коледжів мають недостатню спрямованість на самоорганізацію.

Ключові слова: самоорганізація, критерій, студент, навчально-пізнавальна діяльність, мотивація.

И. П. Гук. Диагностика компонентов самоорганизации учебно-познавательной деятельности студентов медицинских колледжей. В статье обоснована критериальная база исследования самоорганизации учебно-познавательной деятельности студентов медицинских колледжей. Автор утверждает, что достичь высокого уровня качества обучения невозможно без осуществления студентами самоорганизации учебно-познавательной деятельности. Выделены мотивационно-целевой, организационно-планировочный, операционно-исполнительный и рефлексивно-регулятивный структурные компоненты самоорганизации учебно-познавательной деятельности студентов медицинских колледжей, содержание которых учтены при выборе критериальной базы исследования: мотивационно-личностный, когнитивный, деятельностно-результативный, рефлексивный критерии. Установлено, что по мотивационно-личностному критерию на диагностико-моделирующем этапе технологии обеспечения самоорганизации учебно-познавательной деятельности студенты медицинских колледжей имеют недостаточную направленность на самоорганизацию.

Ключевые слова: самоорганизация, критерий, студент, учебно-познавательная деятельность, мотивация.

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